

**A STUDY ON WOMEN'S VULNERABILITY TO ONLINE EXPLOITATION IN INDIA: AN
ANALYSIS OF CASE STUDIES FROM RELIABLE NEWS SOURCES****Mrs J. Wincy Revival Evangelin**PhD Research Scholar, Department of Visual Communication, Hindusthan College of Arts and
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ABSTRACT

New opportunities are opening up for women as a result of the digital revolution. New media environments require women to navigate their digital lives and online privacy. Through this research, we hope to understand some of the factors that contribute to women's vulnerability to online exploitation. Women who have been victims of cybercrime are studied using a qualitative research method. A reliable news source is used to gather case-specific information for this study in order to assure that the content is accurate and reliable. There are a number of obstacles women face in the current media age, and they should be protected and acknowledged. Cybercrime victims, especially women, face a variety of challenges, coping strategies, and wider social repercussions, as we analyze the challenges and coping strategies in this study.

Keywords:

Women's Digital Lives, Online Privacy, New Media, Cybercrime.

INTRODUCTION

In the digital age, technology has revolutionized information transmission, communication and social interactions. New media platforms have emerged within this digital environment, and information and communication technologies have evolved accordingly. The complexity of virtual world interactions has increased as women become more comfortable using them. On new media platforms, this study examines women's experiences with digital privacy. On the internet, it shows how women's experiences are impacted by changes in online privacy.

As technology grows faster and faster, we have seen a plethora of new media platforms developed. Women are particularly affected by these opportunities and challenges.

In today's world, digital footprints are used for communication and forming connections with communities. People share their experiences and information in virtual worlds. When the owner does not give clear permission, this can result in privacy abuse. As a result, new media privacy is important to understanding the subtleties of today's world.

In many ways, new media platforms changed the women's lives. Moreover, they keep changing society on a regular basis in a variety of ways. A case study method used in this study. As well as newspaper articles, it covers the issues surrounding privacy in the context of women's digital experiences. The aim of this research is to depict various aspects of the lives of women on social media, from both a case study and a narrative

perspective. Women's interactions with new media platforms and their privacy implications are explored using real-life narratives.

In the digital world, discussions on women's involvement and the safety of their personal information are the main aim of this study aims to contribute to. By analyzing case studies taken from news articles, we hope to gain insight into how digital empowerment, privacy safeguards, and ethical considerations surround the growing environment of new media can be discussed more comprehensively. As a result of this project, a greater understanding of the complex interactions between new media, privacy, and empowerment will be developed.

The New Media and the Digital Revolution:

Information dissemination and communication have been drastically altered by the digital revolution. As a result of technological advances, traditional media outlets have fused with the digital sphere, creating what is now known as "new media." In addition to content-sharing websites, blogs, podcasts, online forums, social media networks, and other digital tools, these new media platforms also make use of mobile devices. With the digital revolution, privacy, security, and ethical issues have become increasingly complicated, while networking and self-expression have become more accessible. People's interactions, communication, and information obtaining have been profoundly altered by the socio-cultural changes brought about by technology's rapid development. In 2022, Hanshu Wang and Chenyang Zhang discuss how the rise of social media, smartphones, and the internet have revolutionised the digital environment and have had a significant impact on everyday life. Technology has become an integral part of daily life in the form of seamless integration of technology, increased connectivity, and immediate communication. It is a natural consequence of technology becoming a fundamental component of modern life that it affects social dynamics, actions patterns, and power structures. There are both opportunities and challenges associated with new media platforms in the digital age. By democratizing information dissemination, these platforms enable individuals to create, distribute, and consume content. In order to create virtual communities, convey their opinions and share their experiences, Users are empowered through online forums, blogs, podcasts, and social media. Also, these opportunities come with many challenges. Online harassment, spread of fake news and misinformation has made the people to worry about the reliability and ethical use of these platforms. Still, it's a challenge to balance free speech keeping a safe and respectful digital environment. The wide use of digital media basically transformed information, communication, and entertainment. In this modern era, digital interfaces facilitate communication, work, shopping, and content consumption. Constantly, people allowed to be present in both the places physical and virtual places with the help of smartphones, tablets, and computer. In real time, update, respond, and exchange information process can be done with the support of digital platforms. As the flow of information has been constant, many questions have arisen about privacy and mental health, as well as the boundaries between personal and private life.

Women in the Digital Age: Getting Around in New Media Platforms:

In this developing digital age, to manage new media domains, an important role played by women increasingly. Many online platforms used by women through digital technology's rapid adoption. Their basic interactions and roles changed due to this. As digital technologies grows, women are using more online platforms. In order to express themselves digitally, consume, and communicate, a very common way that women used is mobile devices. Information, networks and opportunities reached by women with the support of digital media and that were once limited by social rules.

Due to the growth of new media platforms, it has shaped women's online identities. To open women perspectives, express their opinions and share their experiences, a forum offered for women through multimedia-sharing sites, social media, forums and blogs. Online harassment, personal information security, or the reliability are concerned by many of the people, despite the potential for online dating sites to promote relationships.

With the support of new media platforms in this recent existing digital era, women met all the three goals listed above. In order to show their creativity, tell their own stories as well connect with others who share the same values and interests, feminists used social media. With the help of these platforms, online communities have been formed. Various forums have been created for people with similar interests, including discussion forums,

help forums, and advocacy forums. News, information, and entertainment are more accessible to women now than ever before thanks to digital media

Privacy in the Digital World: A Changing Concept:

In the digital world, a model changes experienced by privacy. Review of its implications required for it. Personal privacy limitations have been changes through the advancements of fast technological and widespread data sharing. People's personal information being collected, stored, and used through digital interactions; there is now a debate recently about how to protect privacy online.

Privacy Vulnerabilities Women Experience in Online Environments:

As digital world keeps changing, women need to think about their privacy. Communication and expression are now possible through technology, but privacy is also being interfered with in different ways. Doxying, cyberbullying, and internet harassment are some of the serious concerns that are disproportionately affecting women. Additionally, gender-based biases and discrimination leave women of all genders vulnerable to cyberattacks. Therefore, there is a need to focus on measures that protect women's privacy and security. The pressing need for women's privacy in the digital sphere is illustrated in this section, which explores the privacy issues women face.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE AND CRITICAL ANALYSIS

It is becoming increasingly difficult to securely manage data on social media platforms, as well as to protect personal information. In order to gain a deeper understanding of these issues, four different studies have been reviewed.

Using social media as an example, Kumar, Saravanakumar, and Deepa (2016) examine the dynamics of privacy on social media. A comprehensive approach to solutions to these issues is emphasized in this study as it illustrates the complexity and effects of online interactions. Consumers should make informed choices using digital platforms and regulators, say the authors.

In 2013, Madden et al. (2013) explored young users' perceptions of privacy. This study calls it the "privacy paradox" because consumers often compromise their privacy regardless of their worries. Furthermore, it highlights concerns about variables affecting young people's privacy choices in terms of how social norms, individual attitudes, and online behavior interact.

As for Rewaria's study (2021), it addresses privacy concerns in social media platforms and legal challenges. In this study, a legal framework is recommended for securing users' data, along with an overview of the changing laws about social media privacy.

Among other ethical considerations, Barrett-Maitland and Lynch (2020) discuss a wider context. In their study, privacy on social media is discussed ethically. According to their study, it is essential for platform design and regulations to be in line with ethical standards and user behavior.

Knowledge Gap and Recommendations:

There are still some gaps in understanding when it comes to social media privacy, despite this research adding insightful discussion. All of the research highlights the importance of decreasing the gap between consumer awareness and actions related to privacy concerns. Still an in-depth analysis about cross-cultural differences in privacy perceptions have not studied by most of the researchers. Closing the gaps in privacy decisions won't be easy without understanding the complex factors that impact users' choices across many cultures and demographics. Studying changes in privacy perceptions and behaviors over time can also reveal how user attitudes and privacy remedies have evolved. According to the studies under consideration, social media privacy is a complex issue. Through these research insights, we are able to gain a more complete understanding of consumer privacy problems, which also highlights the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration in solving them.

OBJECTIVES

- To investigate the changing environment of women's digital involvement and privacy issues.

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- To examine how new media platforms affect women's privacy concerns and online presence.
- Aims to examine how self-expression, community building, and information consumption shape women's digital experiences.
- This paper focuses on women's issues with privacy in digital settings and proposes solutions for improving safety online.

SIGNIFICANCE AND CONTRIBUTION

As this study focuses on supporting women's, it is significant. As well, today's fast-paced digital age, it strengthens the voices of women. It is important to understand the challenges faced by women in online. Since societal structures strongly influenced by digital technology, these challenges should be realized. It exposes women's viewpoints, experiences, and issues regarding new media platforms by investigating their digital lives critically. The analysis of real-world case studies derived from news articles provides a comprehensive view of how women's involvement in the digital world affects their privacy and vulnerabilities.

Users, decision-makers, and suppliers of digital platforms can benefit from this study, which goes beyond academic insight. In this research, the diverse experiences of women with digital technology are revealed, contributing to scholarly discourse. Additionally, women's privacy can be protected and digital literacy can be boosted. Using a case study as the basis for analysis, this study explores how fostering a digital environment where women's voices can be heard in an unhindered manner can foster a link between theory and practice.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A qualitative approach to this study is used by using a case study methodology. To provide a comprehensive understanding of the views and experiences of women who have been victims of online exploitation, this design was chosen. Taking a qualitative approach to the research makes it possible to examine privacy issues in the digital sphere in much more detail.

Sampling strategy: The study chooses five cases of Indian women who have been victims of cybercrime for purposeful sampling. Cases are selected according to their intensity of online exploitation, their range of experience, and their relevance to the study's goals. This sample captures a variety of events in order to ensure a comprehensive investigation.

DATA COLLECTION

Case 1:

In a web of fraud, a victim had just completed a bank transaction. On her phone, a harmless-looking link appeared, tempting her to get the Telegram app. The tempting offer made enticing claims about available part-time jobs. She was curious, so she followed the directions and scanned a QR code, then sent 200 rupees to start the fictitious work. Her optimism quickly turned to despair as she realised that she had lost an incredible 38,999 rupees from her account within minutes.

Case 2:

Here, the victim's experience began when she attempted to return an online order. She decided to cancel her order for a 317-rupee lip balm and called the customer service number she had discovered online. In an unexpected turn of incidents, she got a call from someone posing as an executive of the online store. The caller allegedly instructed her to go on a link on PhonePe to complete her refund. The victim was caught up in a deceptive scheme and lost 19,384 rupees.

Case 3:

A 45-year-old woman victim contacted the Cyber Cell to report that her WhatsApp account had been hacked and that the scammers were contacting her connections under her name and pleading for money under the guise that she needed the money to travel to Odisha. The complainant stated that her residence's Wi-Fi had stopped working, so she complained and requested assistance from telecom service providers. Later, she received a call from someone impersonating a customer service representative telling her to dial 401, which is a code for forwarding calls and messages on numbers that end in 67 and other categories. She was informed that her issue would be resolved by the scammer posing as the executive. The victim afterwards discovered that her

WhatsApp account had been stolen and that messages requesting money on her behalf were being sent to her contacts.

Case 4:

A while back, the victim had celebrated her engagement and subsequent wedding. Her parents shared the wedding invitation on social media and sent out digital copies over WhatsApp to spread the happy news to their wider circle of family and friends. Her pleasure quickly gave way to shock when she realised that an unauthorised person had access to her Instagram account. Her wedding invitation had been used to commit an evil deed, which was a horrifying realisation that awaited her. On the compromised account, the intruder published her wedding invitation along with the ominous statement, "This woman is going to leave her groom and run away from her wedding." Surprisingly, the scoundrel went on to claim a relationship with the woman on a personal level. The woman told her fiancé and her parents about the unauthorised entry. They immediately pushed the situation to the local authorities, which resulted in the police station registering a case against the unidentified offender. The investigation resulted in a shocking discovery for the cops. The Instagram hacking phone number was located in Uttar Pradesh. Working along with their counterparts in the cybercrime police of Uttar Pradesh, the investigation led to the identification of the attacker—someone who was an absolute stranger to the victim and her family.

Case 5:

A 22-year-old B Tech-IT graduate had secretly captured pictures and films of unaware women while they were in public areas, he transformed them into pornographic content and then offered them for sale in Telegram groups. A woman complained to the cybercrime police that someone had snapped a picture of her while she was shopping and that the picture had been morphed and sent to her before being uploaded online. Police have initiated a search for those who engage in such behaviours in and around public locations throughout the city in response to his detention.

CASE ANALYSIS

Case 1:

In this instance, a victim who had just finished a bank transaction became caught up in a complex web of cyber fraud. As she was browsing the Telegram app on her phone, she saw an interesting link that advertised part-time job opportunities. After scanning a QR code, she began the process and transferred 200 rupees. The exhilaration soon turned into dismay as she realized 38,999 rupees were gone from her bank account in minutes. As a result of these events, people are once again reminded how easily they can become the victims of hackers' greed and optimism, suffering both financial loss and emotional turmoil as a result.

Case 2:

A 317 rupees lip balm transaction, which she was trying to cancel online, led to her encounter with the perpetrator. To get help, she contacted a customer service number she found online. The online retailer unexpectedly called her pretending to be a store executive. PhonePe was provided as a means of refund by the caller. The hoax was unknown to her. As a result, she lost 19,384 rupees. From this case, it has been found that more awareness and caution is required in online interactions. How scammers use people's faith in customer service to cheat them explained by it.

Case 3:

A 45-year-old woman was targeted by con artists after her WhatsApp account was hacked. They asked her friends for money in exchange for the hack. As a result of a customer service agent giving her a specific number to dial after asking for help with a Wi-Fi problem, she fell victim to a fraud. Upon attempting to fix her issue, she discovered that her WhatsApp account had been hijacked as a result of following the instructions. Fake messages sent to her acquaintances. Through messages, it asked that she need money for a vacation to Odisha. The risks of identity theft showed from this case. Once their digital identities are stolen, it can be used to ask others for fake money requests.

Case 4:

In this case, a troubling unauthorised entry into a woman's Instagram account took advantage of her happy engagement and wedding celebrations. Through messaging services, her wedding invitation shared on social

media by the victim. This unintentionally gave an unauthorised person access to her account. False and hurtful things also shared by the assailant along with her posted wedding invitation online. The consequences happen once hacked the digital accounts has highlighted in this case. As well, it stresses the importance of protecting personal milestones online.

Case 5:

In a wrong way, technical skills used by a young B Tech-IT graduate. In the public places, photos and videos of unsuspecting women secretly taken by him. Then, he sold them on Telegram groups as explicit content. After her photo was taken, morphed, and shared online during a shopping trip, one victim complained to the cybercrime police. Women are being objectified through digital manipulation in this case due to privacy breaches. Content that is created and distributed without consent must be tightly controlled.

SYNTHESIS OF CASE FINDINGS

The cybercrimes against women can be understand through all these case studies. The patterns, weaknesses, and effects showed by them. An important trends and themes explored by the content analysis. What is means for online safety and privacy, how cybercriminals' work and how victims are affected are explained through this.

a. Manipulative enticements and deceptive claims

The deceitful tactics is used by scammers mostly in all the cases. By gaining women's trust and making them curious, they attempt to get their attention. Through giving quick money, offering easy jobs and fake customer supports, cybercriminals trick the people. The need of more awareness initiated by this pattern. The public should gain a better understanding of scammers' methods and be more cautious when interacting online.

b. Loss of Money and Mental Anxiety

Mental misery and money loss are consistent results in all the case study. The victims' hard-earned money takes away by fraud. A very serious harm and pain caused due to this. Cybercrime also affects the victim's mind. An anxiety, fear, and violation are felt by victims. The need for full support for victims highlighted by the emotional impact. A significance of taking legal action against cybercriminals outlined through this.

c. Digital identity exploitation

How victims' digital identities are misused and used for profit by cybercriminals explored by the case studies. A hacker took over an Instagram account, also spread false information about the victim's personal life in one case. Hackers can cause serious damage through hacked online profiles. Victims' personal and professional lives can be affected by them. Among the most obvious cyber security measures is multi-factor authentication, which includes upgrading passwords regularly to prevent unauthorised access.

d. Towards gender-based targeting and vulnerabilities.

In this age of gender stereotypes and social conditions, it is common for men to target women solely because they are women, exploitation of gender stereotypes and people's weaknesses. There is a perception that women are more trustworthy, which makes women easy targets for cybercrime. And vulnerable to internet scams. Cybercrime is associated with other gender issues, as evidenced by this correlation. In campaigns promoting internet safety, and education programs, gender prejudices need to be eliminated.

e. Need for technological and legal measures.

Women's cybercrime merits a multifaceted approach. In order to prevent future hackers, legal measures should be reworked. The new technologies could also hinder terrorist activities through encryption, two-factor authentication, and artificial intelligence algorithms. Any suspicious activity should be denied as soon as possible.

f. Education and Awareness-Based Empowerment

Education and knowledge are significant for people empowerment. As shown in the case studies, how to stay safe, warning signs and online risks must be learned by women. In order to stay safe, society should give women the knowledge and tools.

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It shows how cybercrime affects women by illustrating the dynamics, strategies, and effects of this type of crime. In order to prevent cybercrime and safeguard women's digital experiences, government agencies, law enforcement, and technology companies must work together.

RECOMMENDATIONS: ENHANCING WOMEN'S DIGITAL SAFETY AND EMPOWERMENT

A wide-scale awareness campaigns should be conducted to improve the women's awareness of cyber threats, cybercriminals' strategies, and safety precautions. Critical thinking and fact-checking are vital to both of these efforts.

With the school curricula, along with workplace training and community activities, digital literacy programmes also must be combined. In these courses, the topics social media etiquette, phishing scams, and secure password usage are included.

Digital platforms should promote multilayered security measures like two-factor authentication, biometric identification, and encryption. Over closer collaboration between cybersecurity experts and technology businesses, there is a way to improve the efficacy of these measures.

Cybercrime Legislation: Encourage the update and strengthening of laws so that harassment and exploitation based on gender are addressed. The penalties for online criminals need to be strengthened, as well as the legal process for victims should be simplified.

In order to give emotional support, swift assistance and legal advice to victims of cybercrime, designed helplines and support networks must be created. Additionally, these structures can alleviate sufferers' emotional suffering.

We must encourage digital companies to invest in cutting-edge algorithms and artificial intelligence (AI) capabilities to ensure user privacy and security. Our content can be moderated more effectively by collaborating to ensure user safety.

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CONCLUSION: MAKING THE DIGITAL WORLD A SAFER PLACE FOR WOMEN

In the world of new media, online privacy and women's digital lives are complex and filled with weaknesses. The financial security, emotional stability, and self-esteem of cybercrime victims are at risk. However, this research has also revealed ways to enhance resilience and empowerment.

Increasingly, women need to protect their digital encounters as technology advances. People, communities, companies, and governments need to work together to achieve their goals, as evidenced by the case studies. Society can support women through encouraging digital literacy, advocating for legal reform, and supporting cyber security measures so they can have a more inclusive and secure digital future.

As a result, this research aims to bring to light the challenges faced by women who have been subjected to cybercrime, illuminating their experiences, and promoting change in the industry. As a result of this research, we hope to create a more secure and equitable online environment where women can be empowered, independent, and confident about using the internet.

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